

Computational modeling of post-myocardial infarction arrhythmias: Insights and predictions

Javier Villar-Valero ^a,*

^a Centro de Investigación e Innovación en Bioingeniería, Universitat Politècnica de València, Valencia, Spain

^b Valencian International University, Valencia, Spain

^c Arrhythmia Department, Heart Institute, Teknon Medical Center, Barcelona, Spain

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ABSTRACT

Background: Ventricular arrhythmias are a significant risk for patients who have suffered a myocardial infarction, with cardiac scar remodeling playing a critical role in arrhythmia development. Understanding the structural and electrical properties of the scar and its surrounding tissue is essential for assessing arrhythmia risk.

Objective: This study aimed to investigate the role of scar anatomy and border zone properties in predicting ventricular arrhythmias, using patient-specific three-dimensional models derived from medical imaging.

Methods: The study involved 29 post-myocardial infarction patients. Comprehensive segmentation of the ventricles was performed to generate 3D models incorporating the scar, its core, and the border zone. Arrhythmia inducibility was assessed through *in silico* simulations using a clinical early-pacing protocol. Different configurations of the border zone were tested, varying fibroblast density and ionic current remodeling.

Results: Reentry was induced in 16 of the 29 virtual patients, 13 of whom also experienced clinical reentry. Conversely, the 13 virtual patients in whom reentry was not induced also did not show reentry clinically. The simulations demonstrated that varying fibrosis density within the same scar structure can lead to different arrhythmic scenarios. Key quantified parameters related to scar anatomy, including the extent of the border zone and conduction channels, were identified as strong predictors of arrhythmia risk.

Conclusion: This study highlights the importance of scar anatomy in post-infarction arrhythmias and provides a novel approach to predicting arrhythmic risk. The findings support the use of patient-specific scar remodeling data for improving clinical risk assessments and guiding therapy to prevent future arrhythmias.

1. Introduction

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), cardiovascular diseases are the leading cause of death worldwide, killing 17.9 million people in 2019, accounting for 32% of all recorded deaths worldwide. Of these deaths, 85% are due to ischemic heart disease and myocardial infarction [1]. In addition, among patients who suffer a myocardial infarction, 10% are at high risk of death in the years following the infarction, with 50% of these deaths caused by ventricular arrhythmias [2]. This occurs because the tissue surrounding the scar formed after the ischemic event undergoes remodeling once the healing process enters the chronic stage [3]. Remodeled tissue, known as the infarct border zone (BZ), forms a substrate that favors the appearance of reentrant conduction circuits and anomalous propagations.

In the chronic phase of myocardial infarction, the ventricle presents a core scar of unexcitable tissue, surrounded by a border zone (BZ),

which experiences electrophysiological changes, namely ionic remodeling of ion channels. These changes lead to alterations in action potential duration (APD) and calcium dynamics [4], which may contribute to abnormal action potential (AP) propagation and the generation of reentrant rhythms. Specifically, experimental studies have recorded longer APD [5] in the BZ than in healthy myocardium, although other studies reported shorter APDs [3].

In addition, experimental studies demonstrate that the BZ undergoes cellular uncoupling and presents fibrosis [4,6], which affects the conduction of the electrical impulse [7,8]. The proliferation of myofibroblasts in the infarct BZ has been experimentally observed [9–11], and the presence of fibrotic areas in the ventricle favors discontinuous conduction [12,13]. The presence of fibrotic tissue is directly related to an increased probability of developing arrhythmias in the atrial

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: btrenor@eln.upv.es (B. Trenor).

and ventricular chambers of the heart [14–18]. In areas with a higher concentration of fibrosis the propagation of electrical impulses is forced to adopt a discontinuous, zigzag pattern as it travels throughout the tissue [19,20].

It has been found that fibrosis favors a unidirectional block in conduction, as there is a disconnection between myocyte clusters and the surrounding normally connected tissue [21,22]. Diffuse fibrosis increases tissue vulnerability to reentry due to heterogeneities in the tissue around the scar, this means that at the entrance of a conduction channel (CC), i.e. conducting corridor connecting two areas of healthy tissue, the tissue is in a refractory state (blocking propagation), but at the exit of the CC, it is excitable, resulting in a unidirectional block [23–25].

Some simulation studies like Kazbanov et al. [26] analyzed the effect of fibrosis quantity and heterogeneity levels on arrhythmias. They concluded that a larger fibrosis size and greater heterogeneity increased the occurrence of triggering arrhythmias.

The use of computational simulations is presented as a highly useful and complementary tool for the analysis of arrhythmias induced under conditions of myocardial infarction. In the context of this study, we leverage the concept of the digital twin, where real patient data are used to construct a virtual model. This model enables the simulation of various pathologies and therapies, offering personalized insights and treatment strategies. The work of Mendonca et al. [27] compiles the main in-silico investigations accurately detailing the models used to represent the BZ. Thus, several studies by Arevalo et al. [28,29] highlight the importance of the size and morphology of the BZ in the generation of reentries, while Sachetto et al. [30] emphasize the importance of the heterogeneities present in the BZ. Finally, the review work conducted by Trayanova et al. [31] provides insight into how modeling and simulation studies can be valuable in guiding the ventricular tachycardia (VT) ablation process. By integrating the digital twin approach, our work aims to enhance the precision and effectiveness of these simulations, ultimately improving patient-specific treatment outcomes.

This research aims to examine the mechanisms underlying the generation of reentry under conditions of myocardial infarction. To achieve this, we have undertaken the construction of 29 customized, anatomically realistic models of infarcted human hearts, using clinical images that represent both the central and border zone (BZ) of the infarct scar. The gap that this study seeks to fill lies in the analysis of the effect of cardiac remodeling on the scar BZ. To date, there is no consensus or comprehensive analysis on this topic using a significant population of real patients. Our work specifically addresses this lack of data and seeks to provide a deeper understanding through research.

We aim to analyze the impact of ionic and structural remodeling in the BZ, as well as to evaluate how the characteristics of the scar influence the process of reentry generation in infarct-affected hearts. The creation of customized cardiac models, incorporating patient data to recreate the arrhythmogenic substrate, allows the simulation of future stages of border zone remodeling not yet observed in the clinic, enabling the prediction of ablation targets.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Clinical data

The Teknon Medical Center (Barcelona) provided data from 57 patients who had suffered myocardial infarction and had undergone an anatomical study of the infarcted area. For each patient, late gadolinium enhancement magnetic resonance imaging (LGE-MRI) was performed, allowing the detection of infarcted tissue and fibrosis in the heart. LGE-MRI was conducted using a 3T scanner (Magnetom Trio™-Tim®, Siemens, Erlangen, Germany). Contrast-enhanced images were acquired 10 min after a bolus injection of 0.2 mmol/kg Gadobutrol (Gadovist®, Bayer Hispania, Barcelona, Spain) with a commercially

available technique that includes free-breathing, ECG-gating, navigator-gating, 3D inversion recovery, and gradient echo. The slice thickness was set at 1.4 mm with no gaps between slices. The field of view was 360 mm, and the matrix size was maintained at 256×256 pixels, resulting in an isotropic resolution of $1.4 \times 1.4 \times 1.4$ mm.

Additional information from these patients, whether they had suffered VT or not, was provided. Of the initial 57 patients, we selected the 29 best patients in terms of image resolution for having a better-balanced sample of cases compared to controls, since of the initial dataset of 57 patients, the majority were controls. Within this selected group, 17 are “control” patients, which refers to those patients who did not present clinical reentry after the ischemic event. The other 12 are patients who did experience clinical reentry, and are considered “cases”. The study complied with the Declaration of Helsinki. The local ethics committee approved the study protocol, and all included participants signed the informed consent.

2.2. 3D model reconstruction

To reconstruct the ventricular regions affected by infarction, a 3D image processing software, ADAS 3D (Galgo Medical, Barcelona, Spain) was employed. The ventricles were segmented into 10 layers, starting from the innermost layer, the endocardium, and progressing towards the outermost layer, the epicardium [32].

To generate the Pixel Signal Intensity (PSI) maps, LGE-MRI images were utilized. These images were color-coded to represent different levels of intensity and were then projected onto each of the 10 layers using a trilinear interpolation algorithm. This approach enabled the creation of a detailed representation of the ventricular tissue, including the scar areas.

To further characterize the scar areas, an algorithm based on PSI values was applied. This algorithm classified the hyperintense zones as either the core or the BZ of the scar using thresholds of $40 \pm 5\%$ and $60 \pm 5\%$ of the maximum intensity, respectively. This analysis provides valuable information for understanding the tissue changes caused by infarction and the impact on ventricular function [32]. Although the tissue is discretized into three distinct zones, these zones are not completely isolated, and the interface between tissues is not discrete. Realistic ventricular models [33] are used to simulate the electrotonic interactions between cells, which attenuate ionic gradients between the border zone and healthy tissue. The pipeline of the 3D model reconstruction can be seen in Fig. 1.

In the LGE-MRI PSI maps, conduction channels (CCs) were defined as continuous corridors of BZ surrounded by the core of the scar or an anatomical barrier connecting 2 areas of healthy zone (HZ) tissue [27,34]. These channels were automatically obtained using the ADAS 3D software. The utilization of ADAS 3D software in conjunction with LGE-MRI images enabled the identification and examination of the electrical conduction path through the ventricular tissue.

2.3. Segmentation and labeling of the different tissues in the constructed volumes

From the segmented images, models of the ventricles were constructed and meshes were generated using MeshGems-Hexa (Distene S.A.S., Bruyères-le-Châtel, France). The resulting meshes contained about 4 million nodes (vertices) and about 3.6 million hexahedral elements, with an average edge length of 0.4 mm.

In the models, the transmural heterogeneity of the ventricular myocardium was incorporated, defining endocardial, mid-myocardial, and epicardial zones, which were adjusted to 17%, 41%, and 42% of the ventricular wall thickness, respectively [35]. In addition, myocardial anisotropy was implemented by defining fiber orientation following the method of Streeter et al. 1969 [34]. Fig. 2 shows an example of a reconstructed model with each tissue labeled.

Fig. 1. Ventricular volume reconstruction process for simulation. The first row illustrates the segmentation process from magnetic resonance images. From left to right: the stack of magnetic resonance images, ventricle segmentation in each magnetic resonance slice, and segmentation of healthy tissue (blue), BZ (gray), and infarct scar core (red). The inset depicts the change in the action potential of the myocytes in the BZ compared to the healthy tissue, and the cube illustrates the arrangement of nodes in the mesh (M denotes myocyte, F denotes fibroblast, and D is the diffusion coefficient varying with cellularity). The second row displays a cross-section of the reconstructed volume with labels for healthy tissue, BZ, and core. On the left, endocardium, mid myocardium, and epicardium labeling, along with their respective fiber directions represented by arrows indicating the direction and conduction orientation.

Fig. 2. Personalized anatomical model of a patient without clinical ventricular tachycardia (VT). (A) Coronal view of the reconstructed 3D biventricular model from delayed-enhancement magnetic resonance imaging (DE-MRI) with detailed segmentation of regions of interest. From top to bottom: Surface of the infarct scar BZ in the biventricular volume (BZ in gray and healthy tissue in blue); Surface of the infarct scar core in the biventricular volume (scar core in red and healthy tissue in blue); Segmentation of the conducting channels in the infarct scar (channels in green and healthy tissue in blue). (B) Coronal section of the biventricular volume and regions of interest (healthy tissue in blue, BZ in gray, and scar core in red). Top: anterior view; bottom: posterior view. (C) Distribution of the conducting channels surrounding the infarct scar (BZ of the scar in gray, scar core in red, and conducting channels in green). Top: coronal view; bottom: axial view.

After thresholds had been applied to the pixel intensity (PSI) to segment the healthy tissue, scar BZ, and scar core zones, these regions were assigned to the volume grids of the ventricles, and each hexahedral element was labeled as HZ, BZ, or core. In addition, in the LGE-MRI PSI maps, conduction channels were defined as continuous corridors of BZ surrounded by the core of the scar connecting two areas of healthy tissue [36]. These channels were automatically obtained using the ADAS 3D software, serving as a guide to follow the sites of interest where reentry was most likely to occur [36]. For detailed information on the construction of our biventricular models, see Ref. [35]. Fig. 3 shows the detail of the 29 reconstructed anatomies., in which each of the elements is labeled as healthy tissue, scar BZ, or scar core.

The locations, dimensions, and arrangement of the scar changed from patient to patient.

2.4. Electrophysiological model

The O’Hara et al. (2011) [33] AP model has been widely adopted in simulating cardiac electrophysiological studies due to its capability of accurately reproducing the human ventricular electrical activity. However, in the case of infarcted hearts, modifications to the model are necessary to account for changes in tissue resulting from the infarction. Various strategies were employed to reproduce changes in conduction patterns and cellularity to account for changes related to myocardial infarction.

Fig. 3. Twenty-nine hearts were reconstructed from real patients. Each patient with unique anatomy and a distinct scar, labeled as healthy tissue (HZ in blue), scar (BZ in green), and scar core (red).

In the present model, the core of the infarct scar is non-conductive tissue. On the other hand, the scar BZ is characterized by the presence of myocytes with altered electrophysiology, and other cell types, such as fibroblasts. To accurately simulate the electrophysiology of the BZ, it is necessary to consider the changes that occur in the tissue because of the infarction. One such change is the reduction of conductivity in the BZ tissue, in both the longitudinal and transverse directions of the fiber compared to healthy tissue. This reduction in conductivity implies a decrease in conduction velocity, which can vary depending on the direction of the fiber and the region of the ventricle but has been estimated to range between 55% and 70% compared to healthy myocytes [27].

Although there is no absolute consensus on the changes that the AP undergoes in the border zone after myocardial infarction [37,38], experimental and simulation studies based on the study of the chronic stage of ionic currents have documented the main changes that reproduce ionic remodeling in BZ myocytes. These studies have shown that there is a reduction in the conductances of the late sodium current (I_{Na}), de L-type calcium current (I_{CaL}), and the fast and slow delayed potassium currents (I_{Kr} and I_{Ks}) [29]. To model the electrophysiology of the BZ, the remodeling of these currents in the ten Tusscher et al. [39] model was taken as a reference, which is widely extended and led to an increase in APD and a decrease in depolarization velocity and maximum plateau potential.

To fit the ionic remodeling of the BZ to the modified O'Hara et al. (2011) model [33], tests were performed on a 3D slab until fitting an increase in APD of 17%, a decrease in depolarization velocity of 45% and a decrease in the maximum plateau potential of 42%. Depolarization velocity is measured as the maximum slope of the action potential at the moment the cell is excited. This slope (rate of depolarization) is closely related to cell excitability (the facility to depolarize and reach a positive potential with a lower stimulus).

The resulting remodeling involves several notable alterations. These include a reduction in the conductance of I_{Na} to 38% of its normal value, a decrease in the I_{CaL} to 23%, and a significant drop in I_{Kr} and I_{Ks} to 80% and 70%, respectively. As explained in the section on model construction, these changes in currents are not isolated to the different nodes of the mesh, but the use of the realistic ventricular myocyte

model allows adjacent nodes to interact with each other. The ionic currents are compensated as a gradient at the interface between tissue zones. These observed changes closely correspond to experimental data collected from cardiomyocytes in the BZ of infarcted hearts [29].

2.5. Modeling fibrosis

In addition to the changes in myocytes, the presence of fibroblasts in the BZ has also a crucial effect on the electrophysiology of the tissue. The fibroblast electrophysiological model by MacCannell et al. (2007) [40] was used to simulate the behavior of fibroblasts in the BZ of the infarction region. Different percentages of fibroblasts were incorporated in the border zone (BZ) by assigning the fibroblast model to a certain percentage of nodes using a probability function. Between 10% and 90% of fibroblast nodes are assigned in the border zone at 10% intervals. If four or more nodes of the same element are assigned as fibroblasts, the entire element is assigned with a different material and reduced conductivity.

In this way, although different percentages of nodes have different effects depending on the border zone anatomy or probability function, different cases can be grouped into similar volume fibroblast percentages. To compare the results of the simulations, these are grouped into intervals of 20% in volume between 10% and 90% for analysis (see results Table 1). The diffusion coefficient of the element connecting fibroblast and myocyte was reduced by 50% [41]. This modification resulted in a decrease of conductivity in regions with a higher concentration of fibroblasts, leading to a reduction in conduction velocity (CV) and increased fractionation of the electric propagation wavefront.

2.6. 3D simulations

The ELVIRA software [42] was used to run simulations. The computation of electrical propagation throughout the ventricles was done by solving the reaction-diffusion monodomain equation:

$$\nabla \cdot (D \nabla V_m) = C_m \frac{\partial V_m}{\partial t} + I_{ion} + I_{stim} \quad (1)$$

This equation describes the relationship between the equivalent conductivity tensor (D), the transmembrane potential (V_m), the membrane capacitance (C_m), and the sum of current equations resulting from ionic gate channels and dynamic changes in ionic concentrations. The finite element method (FEM) was used to solve this equation.

To obtain a realistic representation of CV in the biventricular model, test simulations were conducted in a 3D cubic model of 20 mm \times 20 mm \times 8 mm (see our previous study for details [35]). To consider tissue anisotropy, the longitudinal (σ_L) and transverse (σ_T) conductivities were adjusted to 0.5 S/m and 0.1 S/m, respectively [35]. These adjustments resulted in a CV of 0.61 m/s along the fiber direction and 0.29 m/s perpendicular to the fiber direction. The tissue conductivity in the BZ was reduced by 90% to reduce the propagation speed in this area in both longitudinal and transverse directions, this results in a reduction of around 65% in conduction velocity.

2.7. Simulation framework and protocol

To study the role of the infarct scar, specifically the infarct border zone (BZ), simulations were designed with a total of 232 different configurations corresponding to 29 real patients. For each patient, two critical variables affecting action potential (AP) conduction within the BZ were modified: ionic remodeling of the BZ and fibroblast density within the BZ.

Several simulation scenarios were considered to test different proportions of fibroblasts within the BZ, ranging from 10% to 90% of the total BZ volume, resulting in 4 different configurations per patient. In addition, each simulation was run both in the absence and presence of ionic remodeling.

A pacing protocol is applied to the right ventricular apex to induce arrhythmia. This protocol mimics the clinical protocol applied to the patients from whom the imaging data were taken, at the Teknon medical center in Barcelona [43]. These patients underwent arrhythmia risk assessment and ablation treatment if necessary.

A sequence of six basal stimuli was applied to the right ventricular apex with a Basic Cycle Length (BCL) of 430 ms to stabilize the ionic currents of the digital model. Subsequently, up to three extra stimuli were applied at the same anatomical site, with a progressively reduced coupling interval until reentry is either induced or the refractory period (RP) is reached. The refractory period was defined as the point at which a pulse was so prematurely applied that propagation of the action potential (AP) throughout the ventricle failed due to the non-excitability state of the myocytes.

If the refractory period was reached and no reentry was induced, the coupling interval was set to 20 ms added to the refractory period. The same procedure was repeated with two more extra stimuli until either reentry was induced or three extra stimuli had been applied. The criterion for establishing reentry induction was the emergence of an abnormal propagation of the AP, persistently activating ventricular myocytes over several cycles without further stimulation. Conversely, in the absence of reentry induction, it was considered that the patient's model was not susceptible to reentrant arrhythmia.

For patient 29, an ablation procedure was simulated to study whether this changes the possible occurrence of reentry. This procedure mimics the protocol followed at the Teknon center [44], where the data have been recorded. In this center, ablation of the reentry and exit of the segmented conduction channels is performed. To reproduce this procedure in the simulation, the conductivity of the conduction channels is adjusted to zero, considering them nonconductive. This adjustment is equivalent to ablating the entrance and exit of the channels, since they are isolated by the scar (see Fig. 5).

3. Results

This section describes the main results of 3D simulations performed on customized digital models of infarcted ventricles from specific patients.

3.1. Inducibility of reentrant arrhythmias

Fig. 4 shows the outcome of one of the 3D simulations in which sustained reentry was obtained, patient 21.

At 700 ms, an area within the left ventricle close to the ventricular septum remains in a delayed activation state. This delayed activation finally excites the myocytes within the septum, leading to retrograde propagation of the electric potential from the ventricular base towards the apex.

To validate the results obtained from our 3D simulations, a comparative analysis was conducted between the simulation results following the stipulated stimulation protocol and the corresponding clinical results obtained from the same patients within the hospital setting. For specific cases, we also achieved induction of simulated reentries that were not obtained in the clinical environment.

Table 1 shows the outcome of each simulation; the label "no VT" means that no reentrant arrhythmia was induced after applying the entire stimulation protocol. Conversely, the label "VT" indicates that a reentrant arrhythmia was successfully induced and persisted over multiple cycles. The right column of Table 1 shows the clinical outcome. The last rows of Table 1 indicate the model performance for each configuration concerning the result from the clinic.

The model including a higher volume of fibroblasts within the BZ, and the incorporation of ionic remodeling performed the best in predicting the clinical outcome. Moreover, Table 1 also highlights the following trend: an increase in the number of fibroblasts within the scar BZ leads to an increased susceptibility to reentry induction.

Conversely, among the control patients (infarcted patients without clinical reentry induction), there is a group for whom reentry was not induced across any of the simulated configurations. In contrast, there were virtual patients within this same cohort in which simulated reentry could be induced, which did not happen in the clinical setting.

3.2. Changes in the ionic remodeling within the border zone of the scar

Fig. 5 offers a detailed depiction of two simulations of the same patient under identical conditions, except for the application of ionic remodeling. In one simulation, ionic remodeling was applied, resulting in the absence of reentry induction. Conversely, in the other simulation, ionic remodeling was not introduced into the model, and this modification caused the appearance and maintenance of a reentrant arrhythmia.

To understand the mechanisms underlying the appearance of reentry and the role played by ionic remodeling, as observed in this case and many others, Fig. 5 points out the specific anatomical site within the ventricle where the reentry was initiated. At this critical site, APs from four specific myocytes of interest were extracted and depicted for further examination.

The three snapshots presented on the right-hand side of each graph describe AP propagation within specific temporal windows, represented by dashed vertical lines in the left graphs. The areas of particular interest highlighted with colored spheres, and with their respective AP are depicted in the left graphs.

When ionic remodeling is considered (upper case in Fig. 5), we can observe the excitation of the area depicted with the purple sphere located in the BZ and characterized by modified conductances and a prolonged APD. Furthermore, it can be observed that the wavefront reaches the area pointed out with the blue sphere, characterized as HZ, which is activated. However, the areas depicted with the yellow and orange spheres persistently remain inactive because propagation from the endocardium fails, and because of an alternative block in the transmural propagation that excited the area of the purple sphere. Both blocks effectively prevent the onward propagation and excitation of orange and yellow zones (see Movie S1 in supplemental material).

On the other hand, considering the model without ionic remodeling (bottom case in Fig. 5), the propagation pattern is very similar to

Fig. 4. Temporal evolution of cardiac action potential during simulated reentrant arrhythmia. The illustration depicts patient 21, in whom a reentrant arrhythmia has been induced. The time points correspond to the duration elapsed since the application of the last pulse in the pacing protocol detailed in the lower right inset. The upper row displays a short axis view of the biventricular volume, while the bottom row presents a lateral view of the biventricular volume.

Table 1

Results of all executed simulations. The first column displays the identifier for each of the 29 reconstructed patients, and for each patient, the simulation outcome is presented after applying the stimulation protocol (blue if reentry was not induced and red if reentry could be induced with the protocol). The stimulation protocol is conducted for each patient with 8 different configurations, incorporating 4 fibrosis density values and the application or absence of ionic remodeling. The far-right column indicates the clinical outcome, whether the patient experienced reentry or not. The lower inset illustrates the simulation performance for each configuration by comparing the results with the clinical outcome, with highlighted values representing the highest values for each configuration.

PATIENT	WITHOUT REMODELING				WITH REMODELING				Clinical
	10%-30%	30%-50%	50%-70%	70-90%	10%-30%	30%-50%	50%-70%	70-90%	
1									
2									
3									
4									
5									
6									
7									
8									
9									
10									
11									
12									
13									
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24									
25									
26									
27									
28									
29									
Accuracy	0,5517	0,6552	0,7241	0,6207	0,6207	0,6207	0,7241	0,8276	
Sensitivity	0,0769	0,3077	0,6923	1	0,1538	0,1538	0,4615	0,9231	
Specificity	0,9375	0,9375	0,75	0,3125	1	1	0,9375	0,75	
AUC	0,5072	0,6226	0,7212	0,6563	0,5769	0,5769	0,6995	0,8365	

the previous case, reaching the areas represented as purple and blue spheres. However, in this scenario, propagation succeeds, causing the excitation of areas represented by the yellow and orange spheres.

This analysis indicates that APD prolongation caused by ionic remodeling in myocytes in specific BZ regions prolongs their refractoriness and hampers their excitation upon the arrival of an early stimulus wavefront. In addition to the prolonged APD, ionic remodeling decreases the conductance of sodium current, significantly affecting cellular excitability and decreasing the cell’s capacity to initiate an AP. This phenomenon, concomitant with the attenuation of conduction velocity within the BZ, culminates in propagation extinguishment in specific regions within the myocardial scar surrounding nonconducting infarcted tissue.

3.3. Changes in fibroblasts density in the border zone of the scar

Fig. 6 shows the simulation outcome of a specific patient (patient 1) involving a patient presenting clinical VT, for which reentry can only

be simulated upon a certain threshold of fibroblast density within the BZ. Both models (upper panel and lower panel) are identical, except for the amount of fibroblasts introduced within the BZ. The upper row considers that approximately 70% of the total BZ volume is occupied by fibroblasts, whereas the lower row corresponds to a model considering fibroblasts in 50% of the BZ’s volume.

In the configuration characterized by a higher fibroblast percentage, the AP propagates throughout the biventricular volume. However, due to the deceleration of propagation within the highlighted green zone, a segment of the BZ remains electrically active until it eventually excites healthy tissue, initiating from the ventricular septum and extending towards the right ventricular endocardium. Subsequently, AP propagates, activating the entire volume, and maintaining the reentrant circuit. Conversely, in the case including 50% fibroblasts within the BZ (lower panel in Fig. 6), propagation is faster through the septum, reaching the base of the left ventricle earlier (see Movie S2 in the supplemental material).

Fig. 5. Temporal evolution of action potential along the conduction pathway of patient 29. The depicted action potentials illustrate the action potential at locations marked with colored spheres within the ventricular volume, each potential represented in the color of its corresponding sphere. The top row illustrates a case where ionic remodeling is applied and reentry is not induced, while the bottom row presents the same case without ionic remodeling where reentry is induced. The time instances above the volume snapshots indicate the elapsed time since the last pulse of the stimulation protocol.

Fig. 6. Temporal evolution of cardiac action potential of patient 1. Time instances correspond to the elapsed time since the application of the last pulse of the stimulation protocol. Top row: VT simulation (Patient with 70% fibroblasts in the BZ). Bottom row: No VT simulation (Patient with 50% fibroblasts in the BZ). The conduction pathway facilitating reentry is highlighted in green.

The green-highlighted region, designated as a CC acts as the focal point for reducing action potential velocity, allowing adjacent healthy tissue to repolarize completely and regain excitability. Consequently, this leads to the formation of a novel reentrant circuit and an anomalous propagation of the AP within the ventricular volume.

3.4. Role of conduction channels

Fig. 7 illustrates the replication of an in-silico process involving the ablation of a CC. Two simulations of the same patient are represented, both with identical fibroblast and ion remodeling configurations. However, in one instance, the segmented CCs are blocked, emulating a clinical ablation procedure within a 3D digital simulation.

The upper row of Fig. 7 depicts the wavefront propagation in a model configuration where reentry was induced. After the last stimulus is applied, a reentrant circuit emerges in the left ventricular endocardium through the ventricular septal region, sustaining this pattern for multiple cycles. Conversely, the lower row of Fig. 7 shows that when the region corresponding to CCs becomes inactive, no reentrant circuit can be initiated (see Movie S3 in the supplemental material), simulating clinical ablation.

For each patient within the dataset, the segmented CCs were clinically identified (see methods section), and the cumulative mass of CCs

spanning the entire ventricular volume was quantified in milligrams. Fig. 8 presents a boxplot representation of the total channel mass in the cohort patients, categorized based on the induction or non-induction of reentry under the conditions of maximum fibroblast density and ionic remodeling configuration (last simulated column in Table 1). Specifically, patients experiencing reentry are designated as “cases”, while those with no induced VT are designed as “controls”.

Statistical analysis reveals that the variable denoting “channel mass” significantly discriminates both classes (VT/No VT), with a p-value below 0.05. As observed in panel A of Fig. 8 a higher channel mass corresponds to an increased likelihood of reentry occurrence. This tendency is also observed when classifying patients into controls and cases, using clinical observations (panel B) with a sensitivity and specificity exceeding 0.9 for the classification of clinical reentries (see supplemental material).

In addition to CC mass, other variables measured in the virtual models and their role in the occurrence of reentry were studied: the total percentage of scar core and BZ present in the biventricular volume. These two variables provide information and allow discrimination between cases and controls, both using simulated and clinical results. However, their performance is slightly better when used to classify cases compared to simulated arrhythmias.

Fig. 7. Simulation of conduction channel ablation. Temporal evolution of action potential propagation of patient 28. In the upper row, a configuration with 70% fibroblast elements in the BZ; in the lower row, CCs are blocked simulating an ablation therapy.

Fig. 8. Boxplot of variables calculated from the results. The first column displays the boxplots grouping patients into cases (blue) or controls (red) based on whether arrhythmia was induced or not with an 80% density of fibroblasts in the BZ and applying ionic remodeling. The second column groups patients based on whether they exhibit clinical arrhythmia or not. The variables represented in each boxplot are: The mass of conducting channels expressed in grams of the patient's heart (A and B), the percentage of scar nucleus relative to the total volume of the heart (C and D), and the percentage of BZ relative to the total volume of the heart (E and F).

4. Discussion

In this study, multiple sets of computer simulations of the electrical activity of the heart in patients with myocardial infarction have been performed to better understand the mechanisms underlying the occurrence of post-infarction reentrant arrhythmias. The main findings of this study can be summarized as follows: (i) Twenty-nine patient-specific computational models based on MRI images were reentrant arrhythmia is simulated in patients who also present clinical arrhythmia after application of VT stimulation protocol. (ii) The increase in the proportion of fibroblasts in the BZ is a gradual phenomenon, and the simulation allows for conditions of greater or lesser fibrosis that may not be present clinically yet.

Several model variables related to the patient's anatomy and physiology played a crucial role, such as (iii) ionic remodeling of the scar BZ, which can exert both a proarrhythmic and an antiarrhythmic effect in the initiation of reentrant circuits, (iv) and changes in the cellularity of the BZ tissue, as long as the amount of fibroblasts was not excessive to totally block propagation.

Finally, (v) the most important factor for the appearance of reentry was shown to be the presence of CCs, since even if the ionic remodeling conditions of myocytes in the BZ were modified, specific structures must exist to allow reentrant conduction. In patients who do not present this type of pathway, it was not possible to induce reentry even if aggressive stages of fibrosis were simulated.

4.1. Personalized biventricular models of infarction

In the context of this study, we have generated an extensive collection of highly detailed and personalized patient cases supported by clinical data. Biventricular infarction models were built following a widely accepted methodology [35]. This method aims to accurately reproduce realistic clinical conditions while considering the variability in patient anatomies and the specific configurations of post-infarction scars.

Previous research has also embraced a similar approach to construct datasets of comparable size. For instance, Rodero et al. in 2021 [45] focused on building a realistic dataset that included twenty complete healthy hearts with four chambers. Similarly, an earlier study conducted by Strocchi et al. in 2020 [46] involved the construction of a cohort consisting of twenty-four whole hearts. While these studies included a substantial number of healthy individuals, our study goes further by incorporating highly detailed, patient-specific scar data for post-infarction analysis.

More recent works, such as Bhagirath et al. (2023) [47] with a dataset of 20 post-infarction patients, and Bhagirath et al. (2024) [48] with a dataset of 40 post-infarction patients, have also segmented the scar using pixel intensity-based thresholds. However, unlike our study, these works do not employ complex cellular models nor compare simulated reentrant arrhythmias with clinical reentries, making our approach complementary and more comprehensive in linking scar properties to arrhythmia mechanisms.

In investigations exploring arrhythmias and various fibrosis configurations, special attention has been given to the location and arrangement of myocardial scars. Several 2D studies have investigated how different configurations of scars and blocks can facilitate the formation of reentries [49,50] allowing for an analysis of the diverse mechanisms contributing to infarction.

The present study considers a population comprising 29 complete and highly detailed anatomies of real patients who have experienced an infarction, along with comprehensive information on scars and relevant CCs for the investigation of potential reentrant circuits, which represents a holistic population. Furthermore, this population could be expanded by incorporating more patients or implementing population augmentation techniques using machine learning algorithms, a strategy that is steadily gaining popularity [45].

4.2. Beyond clinical observations: simulating advanced stages of remodeling

In recent years, significant advancements have occurred in the development of complex mathematical models with the capability to simulate the behavior of nearly any system, encompassing biological systems like the electrical functioning of the heart. These models consistently reproduce both typical system behavior and irregularities by introducing modifications that would be unfeasible to implement in the real system, not to mention challenging to measure.

Previous simulation works have integrated disturbances, pharmaceutical interventions, pathologies, therapies, and other interventions [51,52]. The use of computational models for simulating cardiac behavior, particularly post-myocardial infarction, has already gained wide acceptance [27]. Furthermore, simulations of conduction block have been carried out by modeling fibrosis post-infarction to predict arrhythmias [53], and simulations of lengthy stabilization protocols, impossible to replicate in a real heart, have been conducted [54].

What truly distinguishes this work is not only the simulation of a realistic patient's anatomy and scar condition but the ambition to go beyond that, by simulating a plausible future stage for the current patient and making predictions regarding their future condition. This entails forecasting whether a patient is prone to arrhythmia-related mortality based on anatomical predispositions and, if so, estimating the features of this stage. As indicated in the results section, Table 1, for assessing the model's predictive performance, instances in clinical practice where reentry was induced were considered false positives. However, this does not necessarily imply a mistake in the prediction. Rather, it suggests that the required conditions for reentry are not met in the patient at that time. It is plausible that the arrhythmia induced in silico corresponds to a later stage in the patient's remodeling process that has not been manifested yet.

The prerequisites for a reentrant ventricular arrhythmia include an initial "trigger" and an appropriate "substrate" with structurally or electrophysiological heterogeneous properties. In silico simulations enable the modification of these electrical and structural characteristics that have not appeared clinically, allowing the assessment of reentry inducibility. This information is valuable for future efforts aimed at preventing reentry or determining the presence of the necessary substrate, regardless of the remodeling process.

4.3. Ionic remodeling effects on reentrant circuit initiation

The application of ionic remodeling within the BZ of the infarct scar seeks to emulate the ionic modifications that occur in myocytes in the periphery during post-ischemic phases. The ionic remodeling proposed in this study presents modifications in the model of O'Hara et al. 2011 [33,55], on the basis of previous published BZ electrophysiological models using ten Tusscher et al. model [39] as proposed by Arevalo et al. [29].

In general terms, ionic remodeling introduces diverse heterogeneities in the BZ, modifying the action potential durations (APDs) [38], which could result in higher repolarization gradients and refractoriness of action potentials in the border region of the cardiac scar, with possible arrhythmogenic consequences in infarcted hearts [27,56]. However, remodeling in this area is a complex process involving multiple changes; conduction velocity reduction is also presented as a fundamental substrate for the occurrence of reentrant arrhythmias [57]. Despite this, it has been shown that the reduction in sodium current (I_{Na}) implies a decrease in cellular excitability, which under certain structural circumstances may have an antiarrhythmic effect [58] (see Fig. 5).

Therefore, our results, as shown in Table 1, indicate that the effect of remodeling is neither always antiarrhythmic nor proarrhythmic, in agreement with recent research on the effect of ionic remodeling on arrhythmias [59].

4.4. Role of fibroblast proliferation in the occurrence of reentry

In this study, we aimed to simulate the remodeling of the BZ, together with the modifications in the conductances of the ionic currents and the reduction in conduction velocity. In addition, we also aimed to emulate the complex process of structural changes in the BZ of the infarct scar that occurs over time after the ischemic event, specifically the replacement of myocytes in the BZ by fibroblasts [60,61].

By examining various fibroblast densities in the BZ, a significant impact on the occurrence of reentry was observed. Other studies, such as McDowell et al. 2011 [62], have explored how fibroblast density affects susceptibility to arrhythmias. Research such as that of Gomez et al. [41,63] has shown that intermediate densities of diffuse fibroblasts in tissues affected by heart failure increase the vulnerable window of reentry. Our results are in agreement with these studies, showing that patients who develop clinical ventricular tachycardia with a low density of fibroblasts in the BZ also develop it as this density increases until reaching 90% of the tissue. At this point the high fibroblast density impedes conduction and blocks reentry.

In the context of myocardial infarction, research such as that of McDowell et al. [62] analyzed separately the effect of fibroblast density and ionic remodeling. Their study highlighted that the presence of ionic remodeling plays an important role only when fibroblast density is low. In our study, ionic remodeling was not determinant in cases with low fibroblast density. Furthermore, based on our simulations, this work demonstrates that intermediate fibroblast density is the most influential factor in the generation of reentry. Moreover, Mendonca Costa et al. 2018 [27] concluded that chronic stages of myocardial infarction (healed infarcts) are predominantly characterized by fibrosis, following fibroblast activity. In our results, fibroblast activity emerged as the principal cause of arrhythmia inducibility in chronic infarcts. This highlights that structural remodeling plays a more critical role than functional or ionic remodeling in the development of arrhythmias, particularly in advanced or more chronic stages of the disease.

4.5. Role of conduction channels in the occurrence of reentry

As previously explained, CCs represent discrete anatomical structures where reentrant circuit formation is most likely to occur. A commonly employed therapeutic intervention in the treatment of patients with infarction consists of targeted ablation of regions within the BZ that show susceptibility for the origin of reentrant circuits, such as CCs.

The personalized models we constructed from images of infarct patients exhibited significant variability in terms of size, shape, and complexity of scars and BZ. This study provided us with a unique opportunity to analyze how these factors influence the generation of reentry. These findings emerge as key features for prediction and risk stratification in patients with infarcted hearts in future research.

In studies focusing on the shape and location of the scar and BZ, significant contributions stand out. For example, a pioneering study [28] reconstructed MRI-based models of canine hearts with late gadolinium enhancement, revealing that the BZ is crucial for the generation and maintenance of reentry, depending on its morphology and size. Another work [29] developed customized models based on patient images, evidencing that the size and shape of the BZ are key factors in the inducibility of ventricular tachycardias. Our results corroborate that, under conditions of constant ionic remodeling and fibrosis, variations in the shape and size of the BZ and scar may result in the presence or absence of ventricular tachycardia. More recent studies [47,48] also aim to predict post-infarction arrhythmias through algorithms that analyze conduction pathways within the scar. These studies highlight the role of scar-related conduction channels in determining arrhythmic vulnerability, further emphasizing the importance of scar morphology in arrhythmogenesis.

Heterogeneity in the fibrotic zone emerges as a factor favoring the generation of reentry, according to previous studies [50,64]. In addition, the microstructure and morphological characteristics of the scars also play a crucial role, as indicated by recent research [64]. The fragmented shape of the scar, allowing the presence of CCs, has been supported by both simulations [65] and clinical studies [66,67]. In summary, detailed channel characterization stands as a crucial component of our future work, since, regardless of the proposed remodeling, the lack of these essential channels prevents the induction of reentry in clinical cases where ventricular tachycardia is not observed.

5. Limitations of the study

In the present study, we have identified several limitations that, while acknowledged, do not diminish the validity and utility of our research. Firstly, the restricted availability of patient data, focused only on imaging and lacking ventricular electrophysiological information, limits the incorporation of personalized elements such as fiber direction, the His-Purkinje conduction system, and specific conduction velocities. Personalization for each patient is limited to the construction of the patient's anatomy and the segmentation in each case of the scar core, the border zone and the conduction channels. Nevertheless, our meticulous representation of clinical ventricular electrophysiology continues to provide valuable insights in a clinical context, emphasizing infarct scar anatomy. We employed widely adopted and validated methods for reconstructing fiber direction and conduction velocities, though these approaches are generic for each patient.

The absence of experimental data characterizing reentry (ECGs or activation maps) is also a limitation when validating simulated reentries with those recorded in the clinic, but it is possible to compare whether the patients is susceptible to arrhythmia by validating whether or not they have a reentry in the clinic.

The absence of data regarding the temporal evolution of patients and the interval between the ischemic event and image capture is acknowledged as a limitation. Despite this temporal gap, our approach continues to provide significant insights into arrhythmogenic substrates, contributing to a static understanding of complex cardiac phenomena. It even allows for the simulation of temporal evolution by increasing fibroblast density. The definition of sustained arrhythmia, although it may not align completely with clinical standards requiring a longer duration, does not diminish the importance of our research. Despite computational constraints limiting the investigation to a reduced number of cycles, our approach enables a substantial assessment of arrhythmia sustainability and the underlying mechanisms that facilitate sustained reentry pathways.

Although our study excludes mechanical simulation, this limitation does not diminish the relevance of our work in the detailed simulation of cardiac electrophysiology, particularly in the study of arrhythmia inducibility. While the influence of mechanics on electrical activity is recognized [68], the literature has not conclusively demonstrated a significant impact of this phenomenon on the occurrence of reentry. Despite not considering mechanical aspects, our approach provides valuable information about arrhythmogenicity and the contributing factors.

In summary, despite acknowledged limitations, we assert that our work holds significant value and contributes substantially to the field of ventricular electrophysiology, providing valuable insights in a specialized context and enriching the existing scientific literature.

6. Conclusion

In this study we have taken advantage of personalized computational models of a large number of patients to simulate post-myocardial infarction electrical activity, providing realistic representations of the remodeling and pathology of fibrosis and reproducing in a realistic way the pacing protocol used in the clinic. What distinguishes this

field is the ambition to go beyond mere replication, aiming to simulate plausible future stages for current patients and predict their potential conditions.

This involves predicting a patient's susceptibility to arrhythmia-related mortality based on anatomical predispositions and estimating the characteristics of this predicted stage. The fact that simulated reentry appears in high fibrosis density settings for patients who do not show arrhythmias clinically (see Table 1) suggests that the conditions for reentry may not yet have manifested in the patient. It is plausible, and a very interesting finding, that the arrhythmia induced in silico corresponds to a later phase of the patient's remodeling process that has not yet manifested clinically. These findings contribute not only to the understanding of postinfarction arrhythmias but also to the predictive potential of computational models for future clinical outcomes.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Javier Villar-Valero: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Software, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Juan F. Gomez:** Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Supervision. **David Soto-Iglesias:** Investigation, Validation, Writing – review & editing. **Diego Penela:** Conceptualization, Investigation, Validation, Writing – review & editing. **Antonio Berruezo:** Conceptualization, Investigation, Validation, Writing – review & editing. **Beatriz Trenor:** Formal analysis, Investigation, Resources, Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Project administration, Supervision.

Ethics statement

The study complied with the Declaration of Helsinki. The Ethical Approval for this work was done by the Ethical Clinical Research Committee of GRUPO HOSPITALARIO QUIRÓNSALUD-CATALUNYA on the 25th of August 2020 and by the Ethical Research Committee of the Universitat Politècnica de València on the 3rd of February 2021.

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Declaration of competing interest

None declared.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary material related to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.combiomed.2025.110894>.

References

- [1] World Health Organization. Cardiovascular Diseases, 2021, URL <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/cardiovascular-diseases-cvds>.
- [2] J. Bhar-Amato, W. Davies, S. Agarwal, Ventricular arrhythmia after acute myocardial infarction: 'The perfect storm', *Arrhythmia Electrophysiol. Rev.* 6 (3) (2017) 134–139, <http://dx.doi.org/10.15420/aer.2017.24.1>.
- [3] P.C. Ursell, P.I. Gardner, A. Albala, J.J. Fenoglio, A.L. Wit, Structural and electrophysiological changes in the epicardial border zone of canine myocardial infarcts during infarct healing, *Circ. Res.* 56 (3) (1985) 436–451, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1161/01.RES.56.3.436>.
- [4] K.F. Decker, Y. Rudy, Ionic mechanisms of electrophysiological heterogeneity and conduction block in the infarct border zone, *Am. J. Physiol. - Hear. Circ. Physiol.* 299 (5) (2010) 1588–1597, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1152/ajpheart.00362.2010>.
- [5] S.E. Litwin, J.H. Bridge, Enhanced Na(+)-Ca2+ exchange in the infarcted heart. Implications for excitation-contraction coupling, *Circ. Res.* 81 (6) (1997) 1083–1093, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1161/01.RES.81.6.1083>, URL <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/9400390/>.
- [6] J.M. Pinto, P.A. Boyden, Electrical remodeling in ischemia and infarction, *Cardiovasc. Res.* 42 (2) (1999) 284–297, [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0008-6363\(99\)00013-9](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0008-6363(99)00013-9).
- [7] S.M. Dillon, M.A. Allesie, P.C. Ursell, A.L. Wit, Influences of anisotropic tissue structure on reentrant circuits in the epicardial border zone of subacute canine infarcts., *Circ. Res.* 63 (1) (1988) 182–206, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1161/01.RES.63.1.182>, URL <https://www.ahajournals.org/doi/abs/10.1161/01.RES.63.1.182>.
- [8] R.G. Gourdie, C.R. Green, N.J. Severs, Gap junction distribution in adult mammalian myocardium revealed by an anti-peptide antibody and laser scanning confocal microscopy, 1991.
- [9] S. Rohr, Myofibroblasts in diseased hearts: New players in cardiac arrhythmias? *Hear. Rhythm.* 6 (6) (2009) 848–856, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.hrthm.2009.02.038>.
- [10] M. Orini, A.J. Graham, N.T. Srinivasan, F.O. Campos, B.M. Hanson, A. Chow, R.J. Hunter, R.J. Schilling, M. Finlay, M.J. Earley, S. Sporton, M. Dhinoja, M. Lowe, B. Porter, N. Child, C.A. Rinaldi, J. Gill, M. Bishop, P. Taggart, P.D. Lambiase, Evaluation of the reentry vulnerability index to predict ventricular tachycardia circuits using high-density contact mapping, *Hear. Rhythm.* 17 (4) (2020) 576–583, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.hrthm.2019.11.013>.
- [11] K.E. Porter, N.A. Turner, Cardiac fibroblasts: At the heart of myocardial remodeling, *Pharmacol. Ther.* 123 (2) (2009) 255–278, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.pharmthera.2009.05.002>.
- [12] J.M.T. De Bakker, M. Stein, H.V.M. Van Rijen, Three-dimensional anatomic structure as substrate for ventricular tachycardia/ventricular fibrillation, 2005, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.hrthm.2005.03.022>.
- [13] J.M. De Bakker, H.M. Van Rijen, Continuous and discontinuous propagation in heart muscle, *J. Cardiovasc. Electrophysiol.* 17 (5) (2006) 567–573, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-8167.2006.00367.x>.
- [14] J.E. Strain, R.M. Grose, S.M. Factor, J.D. Fisher, Results of endomyocardial biopsy in patients with spontaneous ventricular tachycardia but without apparent structural heart disease, *Circulation* 68 (6) (1983) 1171–1181, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1161/01.CIR.68.6.1171>, URL <http://ahajournals.org>.
- [15] B.T. John, B.K. Tamarappoo, J.L. Titus, W.D. Edwards, W.K. Shen, S.S. Chugh, Global remodeling of the ventricular interstitium in idiopathic myocardial fibrosis and sudden cardiac death, *Hear. Rhythm.* 1 (2) (2004) 141–149, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.hrthm.2004.02.021>, URL <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/15851145/>.
- [16] R.G. Assomull, S.K. Prasad, J. Lyne, G. Smith, E.D. Burman, M. Khan, M.N. Sheppard, P.A. Poole-Wilson, D.J. Pennell, FOCUS ISSUE: CARDIAC IMAGING Cardiovascular Magnetic Resonance, Fibrosis, and Prognosis in Dilated Cardiomyopathy, 2006, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jacc.2006.07.049>, URL www.jacc.org.
- [17] T.H. Everett, J.E. Olgin, Atrial fibrillation and the mechanisms of atrial fibrillation, ISBN: 1997;96:1180, 2007, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.hrthm.2006.12.040>.
- [18] T. Nakai, J. Chandy, K. Nakai, W.H. Bellows, K. Flachsbart, R.J. Lee, J.M. Leung, Histologic assessment of right atrial appendage myocardium in patients with atrial fibrillation after coronary artery bypass graft surgery, *Cardiol.* 108 (2) (2007) 90–96, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1159/000095936>, URL <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/17008797/>.
- [19] J.M. De Bakker, F.J. Van Capelle, M.J. Janse, S. Tasseron, J.T. Vermeulen, N. De Jonge, J.R. Lahpor, Slow conduction in the infarcted human heart: 'Zigzag' course of activation, *Circulation* 88 (3) (1993) 915–926, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1161/01.CIR.88.3.915>.
- [20] P.I. Gardner, P.C. Ursell, J.J. Fenoglio, A.L. Wit, Electrophysiologic and anatomic basis for fractionated electrograms recorded from healed myocardial infarcts., *Circulation* 72 (3) (1985) 596–611, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1161/01.CIR.72.3.596>, URL <https://www.ahajournals.org/doi/abs/10.1161/01.CIR.72.3.596>.
- [21] Initiation of the propagated disturbance, *Proc. R. Soc. Lond. Ser. B - Biological Sci.* 124 (835) (1937) 210–243, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1098/RSPB.1937.0083>, URL <https://royalsocietypublishing.org/doi/10.1098/rspb.1937.0083>.

- [22] H.A. Fozzard, M. Schoenberg, Strength-duration curves in cardiac Purkinje fibres: effects of liminal length and charge distribution, *J. Physiol.* 226 (3) (1972) 593–618, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1113/JPHYSIOL.1972.SP009999>, URL <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/4637625/>.
- [23] K.H. ten Tusscher, A.V. Panfilov, Influence of nonexcitable cells on spiral breakup in two-dimensional and three-dimensional excitable media, *Phys. Rev. E - Stat. Phys. Plasmas, Fluids, Relat. Interdiscip. Top.* 68 (6) (2003) 2–5, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevE.68.062902>.
- [24] N.H.L. Kuijpers, R.H. Keldermann, T. Arts, P.A.J. Hilbers, Computer simulations of successful defibrillation in decoupled and non-uniform cardiac tissue doi:10.1016/j.eupc.2005.03.021 URL <https://academic.oup.com/europace/article/7/s2/S166/520858>.
- [25] M.S. Spach, J.F. Heidlage, P.C. Dolber, R.C. Barr, Mechanism of origin of conduction disturbances in aging human atrial bundles: experimental and model study, *Hear. Rhythm.* 4 (2) (2007) 175–185, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/J.HRTHM.2006.10.023>, URL <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/17275753/>.
- [26] I.V. Kazbanov, K.H. Ten Tusscher, A.V. Panfilov, Effects of Heterogeneous Diffuse Fibrosis on Arrhythmia Dynamics and Mechanism, *Sci. Rep.* 6 (2016) <http://dx.doi.org/10.1038/SREP20835>, URL <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/26861111/>.
- [27] C.M. Costa, G. Plank, C.A. Rinaldi, S.A. Niederer, M.J. Bishop, Modeling the electrophysiological properties of the infarct border zone, *Front. Physiol.* 9 (APR) (2018) 1–14, <http://dx.doi.org/10.3389/fphys.2018.00356>.
- [28] H. Arevalo, G. Plank, P. Helm, H. Halperin, N. Trayanova, Tachycardia in Post-Infarction Hearts: Insights from 3D Image-Based Ventricular Models, *PLoS ONE* 8 (7) (2013) 1–10, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0068872>.
- [29] H.J. Arevalo, F. Vadakkumpadan, E. Guallar, A. Jebb, P. Malamas, K.C. Wu, N.A. Trayanova, Arrhythmia risk stratification of patients after myocardial infarction using personalized heart models, *Nat. Commun.* 7 (May) (2016) 1–8, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1038/ncomms11437>, URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1038/ncomms11437>.
- [30] R. Sachetto Oliveira, B. Martins Rocha, D. Burgarelli, W. Meira, C. Constantinides, R. Weber dos Santos, Performance evaluation of GPU parallelization, space-time adaptive algorithms, and their combination for simulating cardiac electrophysiology, *Int. J. Numer. Methods Biomed. Eng.* 34 (2) (2018) 1–17, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/cnm.2913>.
- [31] N.A. Trayanova, A.N. Doshi, A. Prakosa, How personalized heart modeling can help treatment of lethal arrhythmias: A focus on ventricular tachycardia ablation strategies in post-infarction patients, *Wiley Interdiscip. Rev.: Syst. Biology Med.* 12 (3) (2020) <http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/wsbm.1477>.
- [32] D. Soto-Iglesias, D. Penela, B. Jáuregui, J. Acosta, J. Fernández-Armenta, M. Linhart, G. Zucchelli, V. Syrovnev, F. Zaraket, C. Terés, R.J. Perea, S. Prat-González, A. Doltra, J.T. Ortiz-Pérez, X. Bosch, O. Camara, A. Berruero, Cardiac magnetic resonance-guided ventricular tachycardia substrate ablation, 2020, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jacep.2019.11.004>.
- [33] T. O'Hara, L. Virág, A. Varró, Y. Rudy, Simulation of the undiseased human cardiac ventricular action potential: Model formulation and experimental validation, *PLoS Comput. Biol.* 7 (5) (2011) <http://dx.doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1002061>.
- [34] D.D. Streeter, H.M. Spotnitz, D.P. Patel, J. Ross, E.H. Sonnenblick, Fiber orientation in the canine left ventricle during diastole and systole., *Circ. Res.* 24 (3) (1969) 339–347, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1161/01.RES.24.3.339>.
- [35] A. Lopez-Perez, R. Sebastian, M. Izquierdo, R. Ruiz, M. Bishop, J.M. Ferrero, Personalized cardiac computational models: From clinical data to simulation of infarct-related ventricular tachycardia, *Front. Physiol.* 10 (MAY) (2019) 1–26, <http://dx.doi.org/10.3389/fphys.2019.00580>.
- [36] D. Soto-Iglesias, D. Penela, B. Jáuregui, J. Acosta, J. Fernández-Armenta, M. Linhart, G. Zucchelli, V. Syrovnev, F. Zaraket, C. Terés, R.J. Perea, S. Prat-González, A. Doltra, J.T. Ortiz-Pérez, X. Bosch, O. Camara, A. Berruero, Cardiac Magnetic Resonance-Guided Ventricular Tachycardia Substrate Ablation, *JACC: Clin. Electrophysiol.* 6 (4) (2020) 436–447, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jacep.2019.11.004>.
- [37] M. Amoni, D. Vermoortele, S. Ekhteraei-Tousi, R. Doñate Puertas, G. Gilbert, M. Youness, B. Thienpont, R. Willems, H.L. Roderick, P. Claus, K.R. Sipido, Heterogeneity of Repolarization and Cell-Cell Variability of Cardiomyocyte Remodeling Within the Myocardial Infarction Border Zone Contribute to Arrhythmia Susceptibility, *Circ.: Arrhythmia Electrophysiol.* 16 (5) (2023) E011677, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1161/CIRCEP.122.011677>.
- [38] B. Hegyi, J. Bossuyt, L.G. Griffiths, R. Shimkunas, Z. Coulibaly, Z. Jian, K.N. Grimsrud, C.S. Sondergaard, K.S. Ginsburg, N. Chiamvimonvat, L. Belardinelli, A. Varró, J.G. Papp, P. Pollesello, J. Levijoki, L.T. Izu, W.D. Boyd, T. Bányász, D.M. Bers, Y. Chen-Izu, Complex electrophysiological remodeling in postinfarction ischemic heart failure, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA* 115 (13) (2018) E3036–E3044, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1718211115>.
- [39] K.H. Ten Tusscher, D. Noble, P.J. Noble, A.V. Panfilov, A model for human ventricular tissue, *Am. J. Physiol. - Hear. Circ. Physiol.* 286 (4 55-4) (2004) 1573–1589, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1152/ajpheart.00794.2003>.
- [40] K.A. Maccannell, H. Bazzazi, L. Chilton, Y. Shibukawa, R.B. Clark, W.R. Giles, A Mathematical Model of Electrotonic Interactions between Ventricular Myocytes and Fibroblasts doi:10.1529/biophysj.106.101410.
- [41] J.F. Gomez, K. Cardona, L. Romero, J.M. Ferrero, B. Trenor, Electrophysiological and structural remodeling in heart failure modulate arrhythmogenesis. 1D simulation study, *PLoS ONE* 9 (9) (2014) <http://dx.doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0106602>.
- [42] E.A. Heidenreich, J.M. Ferrero, M. Doblaré, J.F. Rodríguez, Adaptive macro finite elements for the numerical solution of monodomain equations in cardiac electrophysiology, *Ann. Biomed. Eng.* 38 (7) (2010) 2331–2345, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s10439-010-9997-2>.
- [43] J. Villar, J.F. Gomez, D. Soto-Iglesias, D. Penela, A. Berruero, B. Trenor, In-silico Inducibility of Ventricular Tachycardia in Patient-Specific Post-Infarction Ventricular Models, *Comput. Cardiol.* 2022-Septe (2022) 1–4, <http://dx.doi.org/10.22489/CinC.2022.104>.
- [44] A. Berruero, J. Fernández-Armenta, D. Andreu, D. Penela, C. Herczku, R. Evertz, L. Cipolletta, J. Acosta, R. Borrás, E. Arbelo, J.M. Tolosana, J. Brugada, L. Mont, Scar dechanneling, *Circ.: Arrhythmia Electrophysiol.* 8 (2) (2015) 326–336, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1161/CIRCEP.114.002386>.
- [45] C. Rodero, M. Strocchi, M. Marciniak, S. Longobardi, J. Whitaker, M.D. O'Neill, K. Gillette, C. Augustin, G. Plank, E.J. Vigmond, P. Lamata, S.A. Niederer, Linking statistical shape models and simulated function in the healthy adult human heart, *PLoS Comput. Biol.* 17 (4) (2021) 1–28, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1008851>.
- [46] M. Strocchi, C.M. Augustin, M.A. Gsell, E. Karabelas, A. Neic, K. Gillette, O. Razeghi, A.J. Prassel, E.J. Vigmond, E.J. Vigmond, J.M. Behar, J.M. Behar, J. Gould, J. Gould, B. Sidhu, B. Sidhu, C.A. Rinaldi, M.J. Bishop, G. Plank, S.A. Niederer, A publicly available virtual cohort of fourchamber heart meshes for cardiac electromechanics simulations, *PLoS ONE* 15 (6) (2020) 1–26, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0235145>.
- [47] P. Bhagirath, F.O. Campos, P.G. Postema, M.J. Kemme, A.A. Wilde, A.J. Prassel, A. Neic, C.A. Rinaldi, M.J. Götte, G. Plank, M.J. Bishop, Arrhythmogenic vulnerability of re-entrant pathways in post-infarct ventricular tachycardia assessed by advanced computational modelling, *Europace* 25 (9) (2023) 1–9, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1093/europace/euad198>.
- [48] P. Bhagirath, F.O. Campos, H.A. Zaidi, Z. Chen, M. Elliott, J. Gould, M.J. Kemme, A.A. Wilde, M.J. Götte, P.G. Postema, A.J. Prassel, A. Neic, G. Plank, C.A. Rinaldi, M.J. Bishop, Predicting postinfarct ventricular tachycardia by integrating cardiac MRI and advanced computational reentrant pathway analysis, *Hear. Rhythm.* (2024) 1–8, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.hrthm.2024.04.077>.
- [49] T. Kubo, T. Ashihara, T. Tsubouchi, M. Horie, Significance of integrated in silico transmural ventricular wedge preparation models of human non-failing and failing hearts for safety evaluation of drug candidates, *J. Pharmacol. Toxicol. Methods* 83 (2017) 30–41, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.vascn.2016.08.007>.
- [50] C. Liang, K. Wang, Q. Li, J. Bai, H. Zhang, Influence of the distribution of fibrosis within an area of myocardial infarction on wave propagation in ventricular tissue, *Sci. Rep.* 9 (1) (2019) 1–14, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1038/s41598-019-50478-5>.
- [51] N.A. Trayanova, P.M. Boyle, H.J. Arevalo, S. Zahid, Exploring susceptibility to atrial and ventricular arrhythmias resulting from remodeling of the passive electrical properties in the heart: A simulation approach, *Front. Physiol.* 5 (Nov) (2014) 1–12, <http://dx.doi.org/10.3389/fphys.2014.00435>.
- [52] R.H. Clayton, M.J. Bishop, Computational models of ventricular arrhythmia mechanisms: Recent developments and future prospects, *Drug Discov. Today: Dis. Model.* 14 (2014) 17–22, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ddmod.2014.04.002>.
- [53] P.M. Boyle, S. Zahid, N.A. Trayanova, Towards personalized computational modelling of the fibrotic substrate for atrial arrhythmia, *Eur. J. Pac. Arrhythm. Card. Electrophysiol. : J. Work. Groups Card. Pacing, Arrhythm. Card. Cell. Electrophysiol. Eur. Soc. Cardiol.* 18 (2016) iv136–iv145, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1093/europace/euw358>.
- [54] J. Tomek, A. Bueno-Orovio, B. Rodriguez, ToR-ORd-dynCl: an update of the ToR-ORd model of human ventricular cardiomyocyte with dynamic intracellular chloride, 2020, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1101/2020.06.01.127043>, arXiv:https://www.biorxiv.org/content/early/2020/06/01/2020.06.01.127043.full.pdf URL <https://www.biorxiv.org/content/early/2020/06/01/2020.06.01.127043>,
- [55] S. Dutta, A. Mincholé, T.A. Quinn, B. Rodriguez, Electrophysiological properties of computational human ventricular cell action potential models under acute ischemic conditions, *Prog. Biophys. Mol. Biol.* 129 (2017) 40–52, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.pbiomolbio.2017.02.007>.
- [56] M.J. Bishop, A. Connolly, G. Plank, Structural heterogeneity modulates effective refractory period: A mechanism of focal arrhythmia initiation, *PLoS ONE* 9 (10) (2014) <http://dx.doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0109754>.
- [57] B. Han, M.L. Trew, C.M. Zgierski-Johnston, Cardiac conduction velocity, remodeling and arrhythmogenesis, *Cells* 10 (11) (2021) 1–28, <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/cells10112923>.
- [58] J.L. Teixeira-Fonseca, A. Santos-Miranda, J.B. da Silva, L.P. Marques, J.V. Joviano-Santos, P.I.C. Nunes, D. Roman-Campos, A.N.S. Gondim, Eugenol interacts with cardiac sodium channel and reduces heart excitability and arrhythmias, *Life Sci.* 282 (June) (2021) 119761, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.lfs.2021.119761>.
- [59] A.J. Connolly, M.J. Bishop, f₇₉₄-CMC-computational-representations-of-myocardial-infarct-scars-and-implicat-article-706, 10 (2016) 27–40, <http://dx.doi.org/10.4137/CMC.S39708.TYPE>.

- [60] Z. Ceaușu, B. Socea, M. Costache, D. Predescu, D. Șerban, C. Smarandache, I. Pacu, H. Alexandru, A.M. Davițoiu, F. Jacotă-Alexe, C. Cirstoveanu, M. Dimitriu, L. Pleș, M. Ceaușu, Fibroblast involvement in cardiac remodeling and repair under ischemic conditions, *Exp. Ther. Med.* 21 (3) (2021) 1–5, <http://dx.doi.org/10.3892/etm.2021.9700>.
- [61] T. Eschenhagen, A new concept of fibroblast dynamics in post-myocardial infarction remodeling, *J. Clin. Invest.* 128 (5) (2018) 1731–1733, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1172/JCI121079>.
- [62] K.S. McDowell, H.J. Arevalo, M.M. Malekar, N.A. Trayanova, Susceptibility to arrhythmia in the infarcted heart depends on myofibroblast density, *Biophys. J.* 101 (6) (2011) 1307–1315, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.bpj.2011.08.009>.
- [63] J.F. Gomez, K. Cardona, L. Martinez, J. Saiz, B. Trenor, Electrophysiological and structural remodeling in heart failure modulate arrhythmogenesis. 2D simulation study, *PLoS ONE* 9 (7) (2014) <http://dx.doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0103273>.
- [64] G. Balaban, C.M. Costa, B. Porter, B. Halliday, C.A. Rinaldi, S. Prasad, G. Plank, T.F. Ismail, M.J. Bishop, 3D Electrophysiological Modeling of Interstitial Fibrosis Networks and Their Role in Ventricular Arrhythmias in Non-Ischemic Cardiomyopathy, *IEEE Trans. Biomed. Eng.* 67 (11) (2020) 3125–3133, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/TBME.2020.2976924>.
- [65] J. Ringenberg, M. Deo, D. Filgueiras-Rama, G. Pizarro, B. Ibañez, R. Peinado, J.L. Merino, O. Berenfeld, V. Devabhaktuni, Effects of fibrosis morphology on reentrant ventricular tachycardia inducibility and simulation fidelity in patient-derived models, *Clin. Med. Insights: Cardiol.* 8 (Mi) (2014) 1–13, <http://dx.doi.org/10.4137/CMC.S15712>.
- [66] B. Jáuregui, D. Soto-Iglesias, D. Penela, J. Acosta, J. Fernández-Armenta, M. Linhart, A. Ordóñez, R. San Antonio, C. Terés, A. Chauca, J.M. Carreño, C. Scherer, G. Falasconi, S. Prat-González, R.J. Perea, L. Mont, X. Bosch, J.T. Ortiz-Pérez, A. Berruezo, Cardiovascular magnetic resonance determinants of ventricular arrhythmic events after myocardial infarction, *Europace* 24 (6) (2022) 938–947, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1093/europace/euab275>.
- [67] P. Bhagirath, F.O. Campos, C.M. Costa, A.A. Wilde, A.J. Prassl, A. Neic, G. Plank, C.A. Rinaldi, M.J. Götte, M.J. Bishop, Predicting arrhythmia recurrence following catheter ablation for ventricular tachycardia using late gadolinium enhancement magnetic resonance imaging: Implications of varying scar ranges, *Hear. Rhythm.* (2022) 4–10, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.hrthm.2022.05.021>.
- [68] R.H. Keldermann, M.P. Nash, A.V. Panfilov, Modeling cardiac mechano-electrical feedback using reaction-diffusion-mechanics systems, *Phys. D: Nonlinear Phenom.* 238 (2009) 1000–1007, URL <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:264160658>.